

Ferrous-Chlorate Redox System as Initiator of Aqueous Vinyl Polymerization

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Ferrous - Chlorate redox system is a very powerful initiator for the aqueous polymerization of a number of vinyl monomers. With methylmethacrylate, polymerization takes place even in the presence of atmospheric oxygen giving nearly 70% conversion. Endgroups incorporated are hydroxyl and chlorine totalling to an average of one to one and half per chain. Based upon these findings a suitable mechanism of initiation has been proposed.

In a past communication¹ the author has shown that ferrous-bromate redox is a very efficient redox initiator for aqueous vinyl polymerization. In this communication some results of the aqueous polymerization of vinyl monomers, particularly methylmethacrylate by ferrous-chlorate redox system are reported.

Experimental

The monomers from B. D. H. or E. Merck were purified by the usual procedures and stored in a refrigerator. All other reagents were analytical grade products from either E. Merck or B.D.H. and were used without further purification. A stock solution of 0.1M Ferrous sulfate in 0.1M sulfuric acid was prepared.

Aqueous polymerization of purified monomers was carried out in pyrex conical flasks at ambient temperature ($\approx 30^\circ$) under N_2 -atmosphere. Polymerization started immediately after the reactants were mixed with no or a little induction period and proceeded through a sol to a coagulated phase. The reaction was allowed to continue till maximum conversion was obtained or terminated after a definite time by the introduction of hydroquinone. The polymers obtained were filtered, washed several times with distilled water and finally dried in an air oven at 45° . The polymer yield, where necessary, was measured gravimetrically.

Some of the dried samples were purified by the usual method of repeated precipitation² and were then subjected to the dyepartition test³ for characterization of the endgroups incorporated in them. Hydroxyl endgroups (after their chemical transformation to sulfate endgroups) were detected and estimated with the help of methylene blue dye reagent⁴ and halogen endgroups (after their transformation into dye responsive quaternary haliderendgroups) with disulfine blue dye reagent⁵.

For measurements of the optical density of the developed colour a Hilger spectrophotometer was used.

Viscosity measurements of the polymer samples in benzene solution were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and number average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) was obtained from the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ from the relation⁶ $[\eta] = 8.69 \times 10^{-5} \times (\bar{M}_n)^{0.76}$

Results and Discussion

Monomer selectivity: Almost all the water soluble vinyl monomers are polymerized with $Fe^{+2}-ClO_3^-$ redox initiator. The initiator system readily initiates the polymerization of methylmethacrylate, ethylmethacrylate, ethyl acrylate and methyl acrylate in acid aqueous media with no or a little induction period. The maximum conversion is between 60-80% in these cases. Styrene is polymerized only after a prolonged induction period and a low yield of polymer is obtained probably due to its limited solubility in water. Acrylamide and acrylonitrile are also polymerized by this initiator system which, however, fails to initiate the polymerization of acrylic acid and methacrylic acid. The results of polymerization of different monomers are shown in Table 1. % Conversion of monomers into polymers in two hours gives an idea of the relative rates of polymerization of these monomers. For further studies, methylmethacrylate (MMA) has been chosen as the monomer, because it polymerizes with highest rate, gives highest yield of polymer with a higher $[\eta]$ and polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) can be easily purified by the usual method.

Effect of Oxygen: In all polymerization experiments dissolved oxygen of water was removed by flushing through purified nitrogen for ten minutes

TABLE 1—AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION OF VINYL MONOMERS USING $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{ClO}_3^-$ REDOX
 [Monomer]=0.1M, $[\text{ClO}_3^-]=5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$, $[\text{Fe}^{+2}]=1 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$
 Temperature $\approx 30^\circ$

Monomer	Induction period in minutes	% Conversion in 2 hours	$[\eta]$
Methylmethacrylate	Nil	65	2.09
Ethylmethacrylate	2	61	1.98
Ethylacrylate	4	36	1.48
Methylacrylate	2	39	1.63
Styrene*	130	18	1.78
Acrylonitrile	12	27	1.32
Acrylamide	16	35	1.57
Acrylic acid	No polymerization		
Methacrylic acid	"		
Vinyl acetate	"		

* Only 0.02M solution was used because of its limited solubility in water.

before adding the reactants. The induction period depends upon the rapidity of removal of traces of oxygen still present in the reacting solution by the reactive species generated by the initiating system and consequently on its concentration and efficiency. Using even a very low initiator concentration, a little or almost no induction period was observed for MMA polymerization. Particularly for this monomer the system is so efficient that polymerization starts within a few minutes even if the non-deaerated reaction mixture is left open to atmosphere, and limiting conversion is about 70%.

Polymer endgroups: Results of endgroup analysis of PMMA samples are shown in Table 2. Polymer samples have been prepared using a wide range of initiator concentrations in acid aqueous

TABLE 2—ENDGROUP PROFILE OF PMMA OBTAINED BY INITIATION WITH $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{ClO}_3^-$ SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM. [MMA]=0.094 M, N_2 -ATMOSPHERE, TEMPERATURE $\approx 30^\circ$

$[\text{Fe}^{+2}]$ $\text{M} \times 10^3$	$[\text{ClO}_3^-]$ $\text{M} \times 10^3$	pH	$[\eta]$	Endgroup/Chain		
				halogen	hydroxyl	Total
2.5	5.0	3.4	2.48	1.14	0.98	1.52
7.5	5.0	3.4	1.85	0.66	0.27	0.93
25.0	5.0	3.4	1.12	0.87	0.36	1.23
100.0	5.0	3.4	0.69	0.78	0.33	1.11
7.5	20.0	3.4	0.98	1.07	0.27	1.34
7.5	100.0	3.4	0.55	1.23	0.31	1.54
7.5	5.0	3.1	1.80	0.70	0.32	1.02
7.5	5.0	2.3	1.88	0.64	0.28	0.92
7.5	5.0	1.4	1.76	0.67	0.33	1.00

media. The pH of the aqueous media was maintained by sulfuric acid. The expected halogen and hydroxyl endgroups have been detected and estimated. Halogen endgroup content is between 0.64 to 1.23 and hydroxyl endgroup content between 0.27 to 0.38 per polymer molecule. On the average the total endgroup content per polymer molecule is between 1 and 1.5. Compared with $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{BrO}_3^-$ initiator system¹, the present initiator system incorporates more halogen bearing endgroup and less hydroxyl endgroup and also the total functional

endgroup content is a little higher. pH of the reaction media is found to have no appreciable influence on the endgroup profile and $[\eta]$ of the polymers.

Mechanism: That the polymerization is completely inhibited by hydroquinone or D. P. P. H. (diphenyl picryl hydrazyl radical) clearly indicates the free radical nature of the reaction. Since both chlorine and hydroxyl endgroups have been incorporated in the polymers, these must have been formed in the medium in the form of radicals during the reduction of ClO_3^- by Fe^{+2} as suggested by Gleason, Mino and Thomas⁷ and have taken part in the initiation step. Further, Firsching and Rosen⁸ who found halogen and sulfur bearing endgroups in $\text{ClO}_3^- \text{SO}_3^{2-}$ initiated polymers suggested that chlorine catalyst enters the polymer during hypochlorite reduction to chloride. In view of our endgroup results and the suggestion of Firsching and Rosen⁸, the following initiation steps may be suggested.

The chlorine atom may also be generated in the reaction medium by the radical transfer reaction⁹ of OH radicals with the end product Cl^- ions.

If only step (3) produces the initiating radical, then this initiator system becomes equivalent to $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{Cl}_2$ initiator¹⁰ which initiates polymerization by a step similar to (3). That this is not the case is demonstrated by the fact that $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{ClO}_3^-$ system polymerizes MMA many times faster than it is polymerized by $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{Cl}_2$ system. The present initiator system produces more halogen bearing endgroups in the polymers compared with $\text{Fe}^{+2}-\text{BrO}_3^-$ system which suggests that chlorine atom is a better polymerization initiator than bromine atom.

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